

Integrated pest management — weeds

Weed control in wet seeded rice (WSR) in Bangladesh

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Farmers in Bangladesh generally cultivate boro (dry season irrigated) rice as a transplanted crop. Uprooting and subsequent transplanting of seedlings are labor-intensive. Transplanting shock also increases crop growth duration. Rice sown as pregerminated seed on puddled soil and irrigated a few days later has outyielded transplanted rice in many rice-producing countries.

We conducted trials at BRRI, Joydebpur, during boro season to determine WSR performance with regard to weed components and labor requirements for weeding.

Treatments were two planting methods, direct seeding and transplanting, and three weed control methods: hand weeding, herbicidal control with oxadiazon at 0.5 kg ai/ha, and no weed control. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plots were 4 m².

We transplanted 48-d-old BR14 seedlings on 25 Jan 1990 and 58-d-old seedlings on 6 Feb 1991 at 20- x 20-cm spacing. Pregerminated seeds were broadcast on the same days. Seed rates were 45 kg/ha for transplanting and 90 kg/ha for wet seeding. Irrigation water was applied when necessary. Plots were weeded at 20 and 40 d after planting (DP) in both years. Herbicide was applied at 7 DP.

Fertilizer was applied at 80-26-33-40 kg NPKS/ha as urea, triple superphosphate (TSP), muriate of potash (MP), and gypsum. One-third urea, all TSP, MP, and gypsum were basally applied before planting. The rest of the urea was applied in two equal splits at active tillering and panicle initiation stages. An extra 13 kg P/ha was applied at 54 DP in 1990 because of P deficiency. Carbofuran at 15 kg/ha was applied at maximum tillering to control stem borers.

Grain yield of boro rice and labor requirements as influenced by cultivation methods.^a

Cultivation method	Weed control method	Weed density (no./m ²)		Weed weight (g/m ²)		Labor and seed costs ^b (\$/ha)				Grain yield (t/ha)	
		1990	1991	1990	1991	Weeding/spray		Total production costs ^c		1990	1991
						1990	1991	1990	1991		
Transplanting	Hand	176 a	361 a	56.3 a	54.5 a	72	67	147	138	3.5 a	3.7 a
Direct sowing	Hand	153 a	438 a	68.3 a	56.3 a	117	111	144	139	3.7 a	3.4 a
Transplanting	Herbicide	—	—	—	—	2	1.5	76	74	3.3 a	3.5 a
Direct sowing	Herbicide	—	—	—	—	2	1.5	30	29	3.8 a	3.5 a
Transplanting	None	296 b	412 a	298.2 b	158.1 c	—	—	72	72	2.2 b	2.2 b
Direct sowing	None	312 b	576 a	311.9 b	146.6 b	—	—	26	26	2.3 b	2.4 b
	CV (%)	6.5	12.2	28.5	1.7					10.0	7.1

^a Letters in a column compare means at P_{0.05} level by Duncan's multiple range test. ^b Labor cost @ \$1.025/person-day; seed cost @ \$0.269/kg. ^c Labor required for seedling uprooting, transplanting/sowing, herbicide spraying, and hand weeding; includes seed cost.

Labor required for seedling uprooting, transplanting or sowing, herbicide spraying, and weeding was recorded. Weeds from 1 m² were collected prior to weeding, cleaned, and densities determined. Weed dry weights were recorded after oven-drying at 70°C for 72 h. Grain yields from the whole plot were recorded and adjusted to 14% moisture content.

Cynodon dactylon, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Marsilea crenata*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Cyperus difformis*, *Anagallis arvensis*, and *Scirpus mucronatus* were the dominant weed species.

Weed density and weed weight in 1990 were higher in WSR and TPR

weedy check than in the other treatments (see table). Cost of hand weeding in WSR was about twice as much as for transplanted rice. Production costs were similar in both systems (see table). A similar trend was observed in 1991, but there was no significant difference in weed density.

Crop establishment techniques produced no significant yield difference in 1990 (see table). Though the unweeded check had the lowest grain yield, the mean grain yield did not vary because of methods of crop establishment and weed control.

Boro rice can be cultivated as WSR. □

Farming systems

Particle boards from paddy straw

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Rice straw is a cheap, readily available material in rice-growing areas. It is sometimes used as cattle feed or roof thatch, or is returned to the soil. Most rice straw, however, is simply wasted; it is thrown on roads or burned.

We studied an alternative: using

rice straw as the basic raw material for particle boards.

Dry straw was cut into small pieces, finely ground using a commercial grinder, and then sieved. Uniform-sized particles were blended with resin and a hardener. It was then molded into a board and oven-dried under pressure at 45-50°C for 5-6 h. Particle boards were cooled and then subjected to quality tests.

Results indicate that rice straw can be used to produce particle boards that conform to several Indian standards (No. IS-3129/1965, IS-3087/1965, and IS-3478/1966 [see table]).

Rice straw can be used to make soft and hard boards, insulation (for low

Results of quality tests of particle boards from rice straw.

Raw materials	Density (kg/m ³)	Modulus of rupture ^a (kg/cm ²)
1 Rice straw + resin + hardener (5% by wt)	331	135
2 Rice straw + resin + hardener (10% by wt)	680	325
3 Rice straw + resin + hardener (15% by wt)	780	360
4 Rice straw + resin + hardener (20% by wt)	950	389
5 Boards from coconut husk ^b	1310	254
6 Boards from wood dust ^b	890	324
Requirements of IS-3129/1965	< 400	15
Requirements of IS-3087/1965	500-900	90
Requirements of IS-3478/1966	> 900	225

^aModulus of rupture was assessed for 1-cm-thick boards. ^bSource: Indian Plywood Industries Research Institute, Bangalore 22.

temperature), glazed boards, chop boards, and blockboards. Boards with a density of up to 950 kg/m³ were made

by altering the resin type, resin:straw ratio, and pressure while drying. It was possible to produce glazed boards by

using resin abundantly on the surface. Veneer boards can also be manufactured by pressing a resin and straw mixture between two layers of thin wooden boards.

Rice straw boards have low density and are lightweight when compared with boards from wood dust and coconut husk, yet attain higher modulus of rupture (Table 1).

Production costs can be substantially reduced using rice straw as the raw material compared with other materials. Total cost in \$/m² of a 1-cm-thick board is \$2.53 for rice straw, \$3.68 for coconut husk, and \$3.14 for wood dust. □

Evaluation of suitable rice and pigeonpea varieties for intercropping under upland conditions in Orissa, India

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We initiated a trial during 1990 wet season to determine suitable rice and pigeonpea varieties for intercropping under upland conditions in Cuttack. We intercropped rice varieties Annada (105 d duration) and Safed Heera (75 d) with pigeonpea varieties ICPL 85010 (120 d), Bahar (280 d), and T-7 (287 d). We used the recommended fertilizer level of 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha for rice and 20-26-25 kg NPK/ha for pigeonpea. All of the P and K and half of the N were applied in the furrows at seeding. The remaining N was topdressed in sole crops but placed in furrows and mixed into the soil in intercrops.

Based on recommendations of the International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics, Hyderabad, short-duration ICPL 85010 was planted in a 1:1 ratio of rice-pigeonpea and long-duration pigeonpea varieties Bahar and T-7 were used in a 3:1 rice-pigeonpea ratio; all were sown on 11 Jun 1990.

The 11 treatment combinations were randomly allocated in a randomized

Grain yield, land-equivalent ratio, and net monetary returns under different rice + pigeonpea intercropping systems.

Rice + pigeonpea system	Mean grain yield (t/ha)		Land-equivalent ratio	Net monetary returns (\$/ha)
	Main crop	Intercrop		
Safed Heera + ICPL 85010	1.6	0.3	1.56	57.79
Safed Heera + Bahar	1.6	0.8	1.74	194.88
Safed Heera + T-7	1.8	0.6	1.74	157.33
Annada + ICPL 85010	2.2	0.3	1.69	110.93
Annada + Bahar	1.9	0.8	1.64	206.81
Annada + T-7	2.4	0.8	1.88	251.55
Safed Heera alone	1.9	—	1.00	49.13
Annada alone	2.4	—	1.00	86.51
ICPL 85010 alone	0.4	—	1.00	68.53
Bahar alone	0.9	—	1.00	194.84
T-7 alone	0.9	—	1.00	193.86

block design with three replications. The soil of the experimental field is sandy loam alluvial (Inceptisol).

Yield data indicated that Annada (CR222, MW10) intercropped with T-7 produced the highest yields, showed the greatest land-equivalent ratio, and had the maximum net monetary return of \$251.55/ha. It gave an extra net benefit of \$57.70/ha compared with growing T-7 alone. Intercropping rice with the other pigeonpea varieties neither produced higher yields nor extra

monetary returns (see table).

The Safed Heera rice crop had more weeds when it was intercropped with pigeonpea. More than 60% of the Safed Heera crop suffered from sheath blight (ShB) when intercropped with pigeonpea ICPL 85010 in a 1:1 ratio. This increased ShB incidence may be due to increased humidity inside the crop canopies.

Intercropping Annada and T-7 under the studied agroclimatic conditions can be beneficial. □

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.